

Simultaneous Thermoregulated and Sensorial effect of Smart Textiles with Artificial Composite Phase Change Materials (CPCM) incorporated with Carbon Nano Conductive Materials for special workers and extreme weather conditions

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Abstract: *Simultaneous thermoregulated and sensorial effect of smart textiles can be developed by Composite Phase Change Materials (CPCM) by the polymerized combination of carbon nano particles and synthetic polymer like polyurethane, ammonia formaldehyde with the electrospraying coating process for functioning protection and performance of thermoregulated CPCM coated textiles can be performed higher latent heat with durability of maximum number of heating and cooling cycle of wearers like sports, space, undersea low temperature rescue, automobile, medical application, military application, extreme weather and special health & safety users etc as well as provide sensorial effect due to having electrical conductivity of carbon nano particles without hampering physical and chemical properties of fabric structure and the expected smart textiles will perform special properties like breathability, water repellency, soil resistance, wrinkle free property, flame retardency, antistatic property, UV protection and wicking properties where as the earlier development of PCM textiles are performing lower latent heat with lower durability and minimum number of heating and cooling cycle as well as obstructing the common properties of fabric which is not fulfilling the accurate objects of thermoregulated fabric and research on simultaneous thermoregulated and sensorial effect of smart textiles with carbon nano conductive materials for special workers and extreme weather conditions may provide higher latent heat due to using carbon nano particle with electrospraying method, the structural platform of fabric will be stable and such way the performance of thermoregulation and protection properties in CPCM smart textiles will enhance which is the technical beauty and proposed invention of proposed research work on smart textiles.*

Keywords: *Thermoregulated Textiles, Sensorial Textiles, Composite Phase Change Materials (CPCM), Carbon Nano Particles, polymerization, Smart Textiles.*

Introduction

Worldwide growing demand of smart textiles are generating more and more customer's interests in world market. Considering the growth corner smart textile, fashion and technical textile-based market, textile sector has the pinnacle level of scope to apply the proposed research on simultaneous thermoregulation and sensorial effect of smart textile-based fashion and technical product for attracting the value-added customer and smart textile have potential applications for performance garments for people such as special workers like firefighters, undersea rescuers, etc and extreme weather condition. Heating, ventilation and air conditioning accounts for almost half of the energy used in a typical U.S. home and about 13 percent of all energy consumed in the nation. Implications of this energy consumption include negative effects on the environment and climate, wasted money from inefficient heating and cooling of buildings as well as lower

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productivity of office workers because they are too hot or too cold. Sensorial textiles can be easy detection solver of military, rescuer, emergency patient to record heart rate and body temperature. Simultaneous Thermoregulated and Sensorial effect of Smart Textiles with Carbon Nano Conductive Materials is not available in the market of smart textiles although Leading players in the PCM textile market are BASF (Germany), Rubitherm Technologies (Germany), Enlropy solutions Inc. (U.S.), Outlast Technologies (U.S.) who are only dealing with polymer PCM based thermoregualted fabric with lower latent heat, if combined thermoregulated and sensorial effect can be invented the smart textile market can be vibrated with greater fluctuation in new generation of smart textiles.

Background of Thermoregulated and Sensorial Smart Textiles Production up to Recent Development and Technological Growth

Smart textiles are fabrics that contain technologies of mechanical, thermal, chemical, or of combination nature [1]. Smart textiles can be classified as passive, active, or ultra (or very) smart textiles [2]. Passive smart textiles do not respond to the environment; in other words, the design of the textile does not allow it to instantly alter the measured condition one way or the other. For example, antistatic fabrics developed by companies such as Sophitex Ltd. are designed in such a way that their electrostatic discharge (ESD) properties are not influenced by the environment to which they are exposed [3]. Many smart textiles that have electronics incorporated in them are called e-textiles [1]. Wearable smart textiles can sense conductivity and sweat rate of human body [4, 5, 6] as well as the physiological data can be recorded by the wearer [7]. Photovoltaic textiles that absorb light energy and smart clothing can be produced by flexible solar cell [8, 9]. Coating with Nano-particles can enhance the textiles with properties such as anti-bacterial, water-repellence, UV-protection and self-cleaning, while still maintaining breath-ability and tactile properties of the textile [10]. The coating of electrohydrodynamic spraying and electrospraying were successfully utilised as a coating technique to coat textile substrates [11,12] which imparted the waterproof property to the substrate without altering the moisture management and surface properties of the textile substrate [14] and different polymers like conducting polymer-Polypyrrole, superabsorbent polymer, silica aerogel particles [22], melamine formaldehyde [19] and other Phase Change Materials (PCM) [21, 22], coating on fabric provided simultaneous protection and thermophysiological comfort to the wearer [13, 15, 20] like water vapour , thermal resistance and air permeability as wel as the performance was gradually decreased due to repeated laundering and dry-cleaning [17]. Evaluation of thermoregulation performance of coated textiles incorporated with phase change materials (PCMs) was confirmed by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) [16] and the Finite Element Model (FEM) analysis focuses the deformation of individual yarns, the effects of their material properties and fabric structure of coated textiles [18]. When the temperature of environment orbody increases, phase change materials absorb extra heat from environment or body aslatent heat and keep this energy stored. For thermophysiological comfort [23] normal body temperature is 37 °C [24] and skin temperature is 33.4°C [25]. Maintaining a comfort temperature PCM [26] were used for NASA [27, 29-31, 35-37] to make thermoregulated garments and smart textiles have applications of interior textiles, clothing textiles and technical textiles [28]. The composite PCM showed good thermal reliability [32]. PCMs are attractive for heat energy storage technique [33, 34] and organic & inorganic PCMs are available [38-43]. Developers complined that PCM can decrease the fabric thickness required to protect from cold environment [31, 44]. Current PCM based product is being used for bedding, apparel, footwear and nonwoven [45]. Paraffins are organic

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phase change materials which absorb approximately 200 J/g of latent heat during phase change [34]. Chemical bonding is responsible for the above phenomenon as increase in temperature goes to break chemical bonding in the molecules of PCM material causes material to melt resulting in storing heat energy [46]. Phase change materials are theoretically able to change their phase at nearly constant temperature and are able to store large amount of energy [47]. Nano PCMs and glauber salt based PCM were applied for thermoregulation of textiles [48, 49]. Using test parameters simulating the contact conditions between foot and sock in sport activities, the Textile Friction Analyzer is an appropriate device to determine the fabric friction which is related to the sock comfort [52].

Engineering of Latent Heat in Smart Textiles

Latent heat is thermal energy released or absorbed, by a body or a thermodynamic system. Latent heat can be calculated by $Q=ML$, where: Q is the amount of energy released or absorbed during the change of phase of the substance (in kJ), m is the mass of the substance (in kg or in lb), and L is the specific latent heat for a particular substance (kJ kg^{-1}) [50]. The latent heat of fusion is the change from liquid to solid, the latent heat of vaporization is from liquid to gas and the latent heat of sublimation is the change from solid to gas [51].

Adaptability of Nanoconductive Materials for Generation Thermoregulation and Sensorial Textiles

Carbon nanoparticle [56, 57] and polyurethane [58] can be coated on the fabric to form a thermoregulated fabric with more adaptability with human skin comparing to PCM based fabric. Epoxy based [55] nano composite can be used in value added technical puposes and the technology can be [54] applied for the production of simultaneous thermoregulation and sensorial textiles which will also provide the additional performance and protectional application [54] in the area of multidimensional benefit.

Engineering of Sensorial Effect in Smart Textiles

Digital sensors [58] can be applied as garments trimmings and carbon nanoparticle has the property of electrical conductivity can be applied on fabric for the creation of conductive textiles. Emerging flexible and wearable physical sensing platforms for healthcare and biomedical applications [53] for the emergency patient as well different special workers like fire firefighters, rescuers and military personnel for the detection of danger signal in the surrounding zone of operation which may protect the unexpected the danger without implementation of any extra devices.

Significance of Research Gap in Thermoregulated and Sensorial Textiles

The research and development in smart textiles conducted by textile and polymer researcher has been fail to solve technological problem for the production of protection and performance based textiles and earlier investigation prove that the standard technology and production aspects are the core barrier for the standardization and commercialization of smart textiles and there is unlimited technical demand for ensuring novel production and synthesis method for thermoregulated and sensorial textiles. Currently developed only polymer PCM based thermoregulated textiles have so much performance limitations and relatively lower latent heat which is not fulfilling the requirements of thermoregulated textiles and till today there is a huge lack of research and development of smart textile products as reviewed in literature. Proposed research on thermoregulated smart textiles with nano conductive materials, artificial and carbon

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polymerized PCM composite generated by selective nano carbon material and selective synthetic polymer through selective polymerization process and electrospraying coating method can be applied for the application on readymade fabric which will ensure higher latent heat (as per below review), higher number of cooling and heating cycle, as carbon has both heat and electrical conductivity, it will not only control thermoregulation but also sensor can be applied as fashion trimmings in garments and sports wears which may be automatically sense and record the movement of wearer and can be generated data from human body or the environment such as temperature, heart rate, humidity as well as detection of danger signal surrounding of rescuer and military personnel which is not be experimented till now and the output of this research may be a greater and attractive invention for the development of value added smart textiles with thermoregulation and sensorial based textiles as well as improve the textiles with significant and special properties like breathability, water repellence, self cleaning, wrinkle free property, flame retardancy, anti-static property, UV protection, wicking property, antibacterial property etc. comparing to reviewed method and developed thermoregulated textiles and there is no research has been conducted with the proposed materials and method. Smart textiles especially phase change materials in the stage of development process and still many important accomplishments are hidden with the success corner of related researchers due to unavailability of testing standards for clothing containing micro capsulated PCMs, compatibility of materials, matching with material properties and thermal performances, difficult to incorporate PCMs in clothing structure, polymeric shell puts dead weight to clothing, durability of PCM incorporated textile are the question marks to the textile and polymer scientist for smart textiles. Nanoconductive materials with Phase Change Materials (PCMs) can be very output based research because these materials can ensure comfort in thermoregulation process during the physical activities and others like sports, space wears, undersea low temperature rescue, automobile, medical application, military application, extreme weather, health & safety applications etc. and sensorial system can be added an invention of third generation smart textiles. The proposed research can provide simultaneous effect of thermoregulation and sensorial effect in smart textiles is definitely a technological light in the door of smart engineered production Thus, there are ample scopes of doing scientific research on making standardization of technique, increasing latent heat comparing to conventional process, adaptability, durability and suitability of wearer.

Technological Implementation and Technical Beauty in Smart Textiles incorporated with carbon nanoconductive materials

Simultaneous thermoregulated and sensorial effect of fabric with sufficient amount of heating and cooling capability have not yet to be developed in market due to having exact matching of material and lacking technical implementation and limitation and proposed research objectives may focus the reality of imagination in the area of smart textile research.

- (1) Thermoregulated and sensorial effect of fabric can be developed with higher latent heat by adopting a newer technique of polymerization material and electrospraying method of coating.
- (2) An artificial PCM composite generated by selected nanoconductive material and selected synthetic polymer for improved and durable latent heat which can be coated in single part-skin contact and double part to experiment the feasibility under consideration of thermoregulation and wearer comfort.
- (3) Thermoregulation performance of nano conductive PCM textiles by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) [16] and software ABAQUS.

- (4) Advance analysis of FTIR, SEM, DSC, Comfort of Fabric and other common physical and chemical properties of fabric can be done for feasibility to confirm the adaptability, suitability and durability of nanoconductive coated textiles for the wearer.
- (5) Finite Element Model (FEM) can be applied for investigating the deformation of individual yarns, the effects of their material properties and fabric structure of coated textiles [18].

Proposed Research Methodology

Preparation of Composite CPCM

CPCM composite can be generated by selective nano carbon material and selective synthetic polymer. Nanoparticles like clay, Fumed Silica, Carbon Black and synthetic polymer polyethylamine, ammonia formaldehyde can be used as Phase Change Materials (PCM) for making PCM composite. Nanoparticles and synthetic polymer will be synthesized by polymerization process.

Characterization of Composite Phase Change Materials (CPCM)

The CPCM can be tested 1000 times freezing and heating cycle and the compound will be investigated by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), FTIR Spectroscopy and Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC).

Development of CPCM coated textiles: CPCM (**Figure-1**) composite will be applied on selective readymade fabric for the production of thermoregulated fabric (**Figure-2**) both in single side and double side of fabric by electrospraying coating method.

Figure 1: Preparation of CPCM Composite

Figure 2: Development Process of Thermoregulated Fabric

Studies on surface characteristics and physical and chemical structural features of nano conductive PCM coated textiles

Changes in structural features on electrospayed coated can be investigated with the help of scanning electron microscopy (SEM), FTIR Spectroscopy and Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), High-Performance Thin Layer Chromatography (HPLC), Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GCMS), Thin Layer chromatography (TLC) etc for explaining the major observations in these aspects. This will help to understand scientifically the scientific analysis of different changes in textile related property behavior, adaptability, suitability, durability of thermoregulated textiles and sensorial effect of fabric in terms of changes in structural features of carbon conductive PCM.

Heat transfer modelling and simulation

Commercial software ABAQUS can be used to conduct modelling and simulation for the heat transfer study coated fabrics. The fabric geometric model can be developed in ABAQUS.

Sensorial Effect analysis

Sensorial effect can be analyzed by different digital sensor.

Finite Element Model (FEM)

The Finite Element Model (FEM) can be studied for the deformation of individual yarns, the effects of their material properties and fabric structure of coated textiles [18].

Expected Deliverables of review

1. Thermoregulated textiles with maximum number of heating and cooling cycles.
2. Proposed technology will enhance significant comfort properties of textiles.

DECLARATION OF CONFLICTING INTERESTS

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